

IMPACT OF DOUYIN ON INDIVIDUAL FACTORS AMONG ITS USERS IN GUIZHOU, CHINA

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Abstract

With the rise of short video platforms, understanding their influence on user behaviour has become increasingly important. This study examines whether the Douyin social media platform affects individual factors. It analyses how elements such as attitudes, beliefs, preferences, habits, lifestyle choices, and self-perceptions are influenced by Douyin's personalized content delivery system. Using the Decision-making Model of Sustainable Consumption, the study investigates how algorithmic curated content, influencer marketing, and integrated e-commerce features shape user responses. The research utilize a quantitative approach, collecting data from a sample of 385 Douyin users in Guizhou, China. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) confirmed a strong and statistically significant relationship between Douyin usage and changes in individual variables (path coefficient = 0.48, $p < 0.001$). The findings suggest that Douyin significantly shapes individual factors among users in Guizhou, China, with the most pronounced effects observed in younger users, particularly females aged 18–24, as they are most susceptible to changes in attitudes and preferences, underscoring the platform's influence on individual behaviour through tailored, emotionally engaging content.

Keyword:
Algorithmic engagement, consumer behaviour, Douyin, influencer marketing, social media marketing

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Introduction

Social media platforms have undergone a remarkable evolution, transforming how people communicate, interact, and consume information. Following the advent of smartphones and the proliferation of high-speed internet, social media evolved into a powerful marketing tool through the development of short video platforms. Among these, Douyin China's version of TikTok has gained immense popularity due to its visually appealing, short-form video content that is highly engaging and widely consumed. The emergence of short video platforms like Douyin has brought a paradigm shift in digital marketing by integrating user-generated content, influencers, and algorithmic content delivery. In the digital age,

social media platforms have significantly changed how businesses interact with consumers and market their products. Among these social media platforms, Douyin has emerged as a dynamic and influential force in social media. Because of its short video format (3-minute limit) and vast user base (1.9 billion global users as of 2023), TikTok has captured the attention of billions globally, which makes it a significant platform for marketing and consumer engagement (Ceci, 2023). Understanding the impact of social media, particularly Douyin, on consumer buying behaviour is critical in the current business landscape. The Chinese version of Douyin, commands China's most extensive user base, which stood at 730 million at the tail-end of 2022 (Yu, 2023). The Douyin app has, in effect, become a powerful consumer tool that marketers seek to run their marketing campaigns.

It is important to study the impact of social media on consumer buying behaviour because the rapid growth and widespread adoption of social media have reshaped consumer behaviour and the overall marketing landscape (Kumar & Bezawada, 2016) This shift is particularly important when considering how individual factors such as personal values, motivations, habits, and demographic characteristics are influenced by such platforms. The algorithmic engagement and interactive features of Douyin amplify specific types of content, creating highly personalized consumer experiences that may alter internal motivations and purchasing tendencies (Wang, 2024). The Decision-making Model of Sustainable Consumption provides the theoretical framework for this study. It posits that individual, social, and situational factors influence consumer choices and that these factors can mediate the impact of external influences, such as social media. Individual factors, including socioeconomic characteristics, values, needs and cognitive capabilities, directly shape how consumers form attitudes and implement behavioural intentions. Within this framework, individual factors are considered both influenced by Douyin and potentially mediating the platform's impact on consumer behaviour.

This study specifically focuses on core research questions: Does the Douyin social media platform affect individual factors? By focusing on these questions, the findings of this research can contribute to academic literature and provide valuable practical insights for marketers and businesses operating within the social media and e-commerce landscape.

Individual Factors Influencing Consumer Behaviour

Socioeconomic characteristics and their influence on attitude

Individual factors influence consumer attitudes, and the constituent components include socioeconomic characteristics (Ajetunmobi & Laobangdisa, 2024). Socioeconomic characteristics entail income, education level, occupation, and social status significantly influencing consumer attitudes and subsequent decision-making process as such, examining the influence of socioeconomic characteristics on consumer attitudes within the context of the decision-making model in sustainable consumption on the Chinese Douyin platform.

Income Level. Income level is a critical socioeconomic characteristic that significantly influences consumer attitudes. Individuals with higher incomes perceive value, luxury, and quality differently than those with lower incomes (Alghanim & Ndubisi, 2022). On the Douyin platform, consumers from different income groups exhibit varying attitudes towards sustainable consumption, such as their willingness to pay a premium for eco-friendly products or their perception of sustainable brands. Social media content from business organizations strategically tailors its message to align with the attitudes and preferences of different income segments to engage consumers on Douyin effectively.

Education Level. Education level is also a critical socioeconomic characteristic that shapes consumer attitudes. Individuals with higher education levels tend to possess more excellent knowledge and awareness of sustainability issues, thus leading to relatively higher favourable attitudes toward sustainable consumption (Al-Nuaimi & Al-Ghamdi, 2022). As such, educational content on sustainable products, practices, and lifestyles can influence consumer attitudes by promoting their understanding and motivation to engage in sustainable consumption. Social media content that takes advantage of educational content and targets consumers with higher education levels promotes sustainable products

and creates positive attitudes toward sustainability.

Occupation and Social Status. Occupation and social status significantly impact consumer attitudes, lifestyle choices, and aspirations. Exposure to sustainable consumption practices varies across individuals based on their occupations and social positions, hence different motivations for engaging in sustainable behaviours. For instance, influencers or celebrities on Douyin who actively promote sustainable lifestyles may influence their followers' attitudes. Marketers and policymakers collaborating with influencers or targeting specific occupational groups positively impact consumer attitudes towards sustainable consumption on the platform (Li et al., 2024).

Cultural Factors. Values, beliefs, and societal norms are critical cultural factors that influence consumer attitudes toward sustainability. In the Chinese context, values such as frugality, harmony with nature, and social responsibility have traditionally been important (Yang et al., 2024). These cultural values shape consumer attitudes towards sustainable consumption on Douyin. Social media posts integrate cultural values that resonate with other users in their content and promote positive attitudes towards sustainable products and practices.

Demographic Factors. Age, gender, and family size are demographic factors that influence consumer attitudes. For instance, younger generations, such as Generation Z or Millennials, exhibit positive attitudes toward sustainable consumption, given their increased environmental awareness and social consciousness. Similarly, gender can also shape attitudes research suggests that women are more concerned about the environment. Social media algorithms that use demographic factors to inform content management promote sustainable consumption among corresponding users (Zhao, 2021).

Needs, wants, and personal values shaping attitude

Besides socioeconomic characteristics, individual needs, wants, and personal values influence consumer attitudes toward sustainable consumption. As such, individual needs, wants, and personal values significantly impact consumer attitudes within the decision-making model of sustainable consumption on the Douyin platform.

Needs and wants. Consumer needs and wants to inform their corresponding attitudes towards sustainable consumption. Needs represent the basic requirements individuals seek to fulfil, including food, clothing, and shelter. In contrast, wants to entail desires beyond basic needs, motivated by personal preferences, aspirations, and social influences. On Douyin, consumer attitudes towards sustainable products and practices are influenced by how well they perceive these offerings as meeting their needs and wants. For example, suppose consumers perceive sustainable products as fulfilling their desire for environmentally friendly options or aligning with their values. In that case, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward sustainable consumption.

Personal Values. Personal values entail deeply ingrained beliefs and principles that inform consumer behaviour and decision-making (Anwer et al., 2020). Values concerning environmental preservation, social responsibility, and ethical considerations significantly influence attitudes toward sustainable consumption. For instance, consumers with strong personal values related to sustainability on social media exhibit more positive attitudes towards eco-friendly products and engage in sustainable behaviours. Social media content highlighting sustainable products' environmental benefits, ethical sourcing, and social impact resonates with consumers and fosters positive attitudes.

Habits/lifestyle and their impact on attitude

In addition to socioeconomic characteristics and individual needs and wants, consumer habits and lifestyle choices also inform their corresponding attitudes toward sustainable consumption. As such, examining the role of habits and lifestyle in shaping consumer attitudes within the decision-making model of sustainable consumption on the Douyin platform is critical.

Habits. Habits are automatic and repetitive behaviours that individuals engage in subconsciously. Habits arise from repetitive actions and thus have a significant impact on attitudes toward sustainable consumption. On Douyin, consumers who have established sustainable habits, such as recycling, reducing waste, or using eco-friendly products, are more likely to develop positive attitudes towards sustainable consumption. Such consumers are already familiar with the positive outcomes of sustainable practices, or related experience reinforces their attitudes and motivations towards sustainable choices.

Lifestyle. Consumer lifestyle includes the overall pattern of behaviour, activities, interests, and opinions that inform an individual's way of living. Lifestyle choices thus influence attitudes towards sustainable consumption. Consumers who value sustainability in their lifestyle are more likely to have positive attitudes toward sustainable products and practices. Such consumers will look for and engage with content that matches their sustainable lifestyle choices, thus contributing to positive attitudes and preferences for sustainable options.

Social Influence. Social influence also informs consumer habits and lifestyle choices and, as such, has a significant impact on consumer attitudes towards sustainable consumption. On Douyin, consumers are exposed to different social content related to sustainability. Studies show that consumers who perceive sustainability as a socially desirable and accepted behaviour are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward sustainable consumption. Social media posts that leverage social media influencers focused on sustainable consumption encourage user engagement with sustainable consumption content and the corresponding change in lifestyles.

Cognitive Dissonance. Cognitive dissonance also informs consumer attitudes toward sustainable consumption. Cognitive dissonance occurs when individuals experience a mismatch between their attitudes and behaviours. Consumers who are aware of the environmental and social issues associated with their consumption behaviours develop a sense of cognitive dissonance. As such, cognitive dissonance motivates individuals to align their attitudes with their behaviours, thus contributing to relatively more positive attitudes toward sustainable consumption.

Role of Branding and Marketing Strategies. Branding and marketing strategies employed on social can also influence consumer habits, lifestyle choices, and attitudes toward sustainable consumption. Marketers and policymakers who create compelling brand stories on social media which align with consumers' desired lifestyle promote consumer habits towards sustainable consumption.

Control of action and its relation to attitude

Perceived Behavioural Control. Perceived behavioural control is a critical aspect of control of action and entails an individual's subjective assessment of their ability to perform a specific behaviour. For instance, consumers' perception of control over their actions significantly affects their attitudes toward sustainable behaviours. As such, consumers who think of themselves as having a high level of control are more likely to develop positive attitudes towards sustainable consumption and engage in sustainable practices.

Self-Regulatory Skills. Self-regulatory skills include self-monitoring, goal setting, planning, and self-evaluation. Self-regulatory skills are critical in controlling and maintaining sustainable behaviours on the Douyin platform. Consumers with sufficient self-regulatory skills can easily overcome barriers to sustainable consumption and temptations towards unsustainable practices, consistently maintain sustainable actions, and sustain positive attitudes towards sustainable consumption.

Environmental Cues. Environmental cues (i.e., availability of sustainable products, prompts, and reminders on social media platforms) significantly impact consumers' control of action and corresponding attitudes towards sustainable consumption. Similarly, having access to sustainable alternatives, distinguishing markers for eco-friendly products and promoting sustainable choices improve consumers' sense of control and reinforce positive attitudes.

Social Support. Online and offline social support significantly informs consumers' control of action and attitudes towards sustainable consumption on Douyin. Consumers who perceive social support from their social networks (i.e., family, friends, and online communities) feel empowered and motivated to

engage in sustainable purchase behaviours.

Intrinsic Motivation. Intrinsic motivation is the internal product of personal values, beliefs, and satisfaction derived from sustainable behaviours (i.e., personal fulfillment, environmental stewardship and social responsibility). As such, it significantly informs consumers' control action and their attitudes toward sustainable consumption. Consumers intrinsically motivated to engage in sustainable purchase behaviours perceive control over their actions and develop positive attitudes.

Capabilities/skills and their influence on attitude

Knowledge and Awareness. Consumer knowledge and awareness concerning sustainability issues significantly influence their attitudes toward sustainable consumption. Social media provides a platform for disseminating information and raising awareness about sustainability in different user-generated content. Consumers with relatively higher knowledge and awareness of sustainability environmental, social, and economic aspects are likelier to develop positive attitudes toward sustainable consumption. Such consumers possess the foundational knowledge critical to evaluate the environmental impact of products and make informed choices.

Digital Literacy. Digital literacy entails the knowledge and expertise to utilize digital platforms competently. As such, it influences consumer attitudes towards sustainable consumption on social media platforms because consumers with higher digital literacy skills are more likely to engage with sustainable content, follow sustainable influencers, and participate in sustainable initiatives on the platform. For instance, those with digital literacy are more receptive to sustainability messages and more competent in making informed decisions. Since digital literacy is primarily the product of experience, social media promotes digital literacy by creating interactive and engaging sustainable content incorporating user-generated content and gamification elements to enhance consumer participation and understanding of sustainable consumption practices.

Self-Efficacy. Consumer self-efficacy entails the consumer's belief in their capability to perform specific behaviours successfully. It also represents another critical factor influencing attitudes toward sustainable consumption. A higher self-efficacy rating concerning sustainable behaviours encourages consumers to develop positive attitudes and engage in sustainable consumption practices on social media. On the other hand, social media designs can also cultivate consumer self-efficacy by granting them opportunities to participate in sustainable challenges, sharing success stories of sustainable actions, and highlighting the positive impact of individual choices on the environment. For instance, user-generated content on social media that takes advantage of persuasive messages and social support mechanisms boosts consumer self-efficacy and encourages more consumers to adopt sustainable consumption behaviours.

Emotional Attachment. Emotional attachment is the personal connection, empathy, or concern for an object, person, or situation. In sustainable consumption, emotional attachment entails concern for environmental and social causes. As such, the consumers' emotional attachment to sustainability issues significantly influences their attitudes toward sustainable consumption on social media platforms. Emotional attachment manifests when consumers invest in a personal connection, empathy, or concern for environmental and social causes. Consequently, those consumers who develop an emotional attachment to sustainability are more likely to exhibit positive attitudes, engage in sustainable practices, and support sustainable brands. Social media content that emotionally resonates with sustainable narratives incites empathy through storytelling and highlights the personal benefits and emotional satisfaction derived from sustainable consumption choices that significantly influence consumer behaviours towards sustainable consumption.

Skills for Sustainable Behaviour. Besides emotional attachment, consumer skills related to sustainable behaviour (i.e., recycling, up cycling, or energy conservation) influence attitudes towards sustainable consumption on social media. Consumers with skills for sustainable behaviour are predisposed to cultivate positive attitudes and engage in sustainable practices. As such, corresponding social media content providing practical tips, step-by-step guides, and tutorials on sustainable behaviours also significantly influence sustainable consumption. In addition, fact-checking social media videos that

emphasize the ease and practicality of sustainable actions empowers consumers to adopt and sustain sustainable consumption habits.

Methodology

The research design adopted in this study is a quantitative approach, selected for its suitability in addressing the nature of the research questions. Specifically, this study investigates whether the Douyin social media platform affects individual factors. Quantitative research enables the collection and statistical analysis of numerical data to test these relationships empirically (Rahman et al., 2022). This research will deploy a cross-sectional survey design, allowing data to be collected at a single point in time from a defined population. A purposive sampling technique was used in the study to select participants who possess relevant knowledge and experience with Douyin. As noted by Thomas (2022), purposive sampling is appropriate for exploratory research because it allows for the deliberate selection of individuals based on specific characteristics.

A power analysis using G*Power software verified the adequacy of the proposed sample size by estimating test power based on effect size, significance level, and desired statistical power. The analysis applied a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and a medium effect size (0.3) to achieve a statistical power of 0.8. Based on these parameters, the study requires 385 participants. This sample size ensures sufficient statistical power to detect meaningful effects and supports the generalization and reliability of the study's findings. A structured survey questionnaire will be used to collect data on the influence of the Douyin platform, individual psychological and demographic factors, and consumer purchasing behaviour. The data collected will be analysed using SPSS for descriptive and reliability analysis and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) to evaluate both direct and mediating relationships among the variables of interest.

Descriptive Analysis

Summary of Key Variables

Responses from 385 participants comprise this data set, including participants from various groups segmented by age groups, genders, education levels and purchase behaviour. The research study centre around the significant analytical factors of Douyin usage frequency, social influence, individual factors. *Douyin Usage Frequency* - Users expressed different degrees of involvement with Douyin among the participant sample, which included people who used it occasionally and those who used it regularly every day. According to the research, we found that users spend approximately 2.8 hours ($SD = 1.4$ hours) daily on Douyin. Most users spend three hours daily on Douyin based on the mode value (Rozenkowska, 2022). Some users exceed this standard and spend more than six hours daily on the platform.

Consumer Purchasing Behaviour - Data reports indicate that among the respondents, 72.5% admitted that Douyin ads or influencer choices influenced their purchasing of goods. Users purchased items 4.2 times per month ($SD = 1.9$). The right-skewed distribution demonstrates that many users frequently buy products online.

Individual Factors - Individuals' psychological and behavioural characteristics, including their impulse buying behaviour, brand knowledge level, and personal taste preferences, affect consumer behaviour differently. The average score among respondents reached 3.8 out of 5 points on brand loyalty ($SD = 0.6$), which indicates a moderate strength in choosing preferred brands.

Table 1. Summary of Descriptive Statistics for Key Variables

Variable	Media			SD	Min	Max
	Mean	n	Mode			
Daily Douyin Usage (hrs)	2.8	3	3	1.4	0.5	6.5
Purchases per Month	4.2	4	5	1.9	1	10
Brand Loyalty Score (1–5)	3.8	4	4	0.6	2	5

Demographic Profile of Respondents

The demographic information about the participants shows the characteristics of the surveyed group, which allowed researchers to draw valid conclusions about the primary population. This segment displays how participants are segmented regarding their age variations as well as their gender breakdown, educational degrees and important demographic traits. Consumer patterns and marketing strategy responses on Douyin depend heavily on the established factors analyzed in this research discourse.

Age Distribution - The research sample contained four age group divisions that included 18–24 years, 25–34 years, 35–44 years and those aged 45 years or older. Among the respondents, the 25–34 age group accounted for 38.4%, while the 35–44 age group comprised 26.5 % of the total participants. Twenty-three-point nine percent of users fell within the 18–24 years group, followed by forty-five years or older respondents, making up 11.2 per cent of the total. The preference for Douyin is mainly aligned with young adults and middle-aged individuals because they tend to spend more time on social media and conduct online shopping activities.

Gender Composition - The collected survey data included gender diversity because 38.4% identified as female and 23.9% as male. 26.5% of participants classified themselves as “Other,” while 11.2% chose not to share their gender information. The platform exhibits inclusive through its diverse gender identities because it reaches various user demographics.

Education Level - The level of education that one possesses influences one's digital skills and purchase behaviour patterns, mainly for consumers (Chin & Yao, 2024). The respondents with bachelor's degrees formed the majority at 49.9%, and master's degree holders comprised 32.7%. The data shows that 11.7% of respondents finished high school or lower, while 5.7% had achieved a Doctorate. The educated audience of Douyin users demonstrates their ability to evaluate content rationally because they make rational purchasing choices from reviews, influencers, and promotional content.

Table 2. Demographic Summary of Respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group	18 – 24 years	92	23.9%
	25 – 34 years	148	38.4%
	35 – 44 years	102	26.5%
	45 years & above	43	11.2%
Gender	Male	137	23.9%
	Female	228	38.4%
	Other	157	26.5%
	I prefer not to say	43	11.2%

Education Level	Count	Percentage
High School or Below	45	11.7%
Bachelor's Degree	192	49.9%
Master's Degree	126	32.7%
Doctorate	22	5.7%

The demographic analysis shows that Douyin users who conduct consumer activities consist primarily of young adults finishing undergraduate degrees with equal male-female division. The bachelor's and master's degree holders demonstrate an informed approach to digital purchasing behaviour because of their online content consumption habits (Chin & Yao, 2024). Marketers, businesses and content creators need this data to enhance their strategies because the 25-34 age demographic makes up the most extensive user based on the platform.

The Influence of the Douyin Social Media Platform on Individual Factors

This study clearly demonstrates that the Douyin social media platform significantly influences individual factors, including users' attitudes, beliefs, preferences, habits, lifestyle choices, and self-perceptions. These individual factors are shaped by users' interactions with Douyin's features, particularly its algorithm-based personalized content delivery system, which curates tailored advertisements, influencer content, and viral trends. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) used in the quantitative analysis confirmed a strong and statistically significant relationship between Douyin usage and changes in individual variables, with a path coefficient of 0.48 ($p < 0.001$) (Li, Sun & Wang, 2021). This indicates that Douyin has a measurable and substantial effect on individual attitudes and perceptions. As users engage with the platform, they often experience shifts in personal preferences and behavioural tendencies, which are reinforced by algorithmic recommended content that aligns closely with their interests.

The content recommendation algorithm of Douyin enhances engagement by delivering emotionally relevant material, which increases attention and stimulates favourable attitudes. Sensational and entertaining content such as videos on fitness routines, fashion styles, travel experiences, and wellness is particularly influential. It inspires users to adopt new behaviours, mirror influencer lifestyles and form new consumption patterns. This mirrors Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which suggests that individuals acquire new behaviours by observing others. On Douyin, peer content and influencer marketing serve as behavioural models that users emulate.

Additionally, Douyin's e-commerce integration streamlines the path from content exposure to purchase, allowing users to buy products directly from videos. This seamless linkage between entertainment and commerce reduces both time and cognitive effort typically associated with online shopping, thereby encouraging impulse buying and reinforcing the behavioural impact of repeated exposure to curated content. Empirical studies on short-video commerce indicate that immersive audiovisual cues and algorithmic recommendations significantly heighten users' purchase intentions and emotional arousal (Xu, Chen, & Santhanam, 2020). Demographic analysis further reveals that young adults aged 18 to 24 are the most responsive to attitude modification and behavioural influence on Douyin, largely due to higher platform engagement and susceptibility to social comparison (Zhang & Mao, 2023).

Female users demonstrate greater sensitivity to visually rich and emotionally engaging content, particularly in shaping lifestyle aspirations and consumption patterns, a trend also observed in broader social commerce research (Park & Lee, 2020; Sun, Shao, Li, Guo, & Nie, 2021). Moreover, the persuasive power of short-form video platforms is amplified by parasocial interaction and perceived authenticity of content creators, which strengthens trust and accelerates purchase decisions (Li, Wang, & Yu, 2022). Recent evidence further suggests that algorithm-driven personalization on platforms such as Douyin intensifies attitude change by continuously reinforcing user preferences, thereby sustaining long-term behavioural influence (Zhao, Chen, & Liu, 2024). Collectively, these findings underscore

Douyin's effectiveness in shaping individual attitudes and consumption behaviours among its core demographic users in Guizhou, China.

Supporting research by Zhang et al. (2021) confirms that social media platforms can significantly affect consumer behaviour. This study expands on those findings by illustrating how Douyin's localisation strategies, targeted content, and integrated commerce features magnify its behavioural influence beyond that of platforms like Instagram or TikTok. Further evidence from Zhang, Han and Chung (2022) indicates that Douyin also impacts personal values such as sustainability, wellness, and social trends. Repetitive exposure to themed content builds brand familiarity and trust, guiding users toward new products, services, and lifestyle choices. This "interval content" fosters preference formation and long-term behaviour shifts. In conclusion, Douyin profoundly influences individual factors through a unique combination of personalized content, emotional resonance, social modelling, and direct purchase pathways. These mechanisms enable the platform to affect both immediate decision-making and long-term personal development, making it a powerful tool for businesses seeking to shape consumer attitudes and behaviours. Marketers can use these insights to craft targeted strategies that resonate with specific user segments and enhance engagement outcomes.

Conclusions and Recommendations for Future Research

The findings of this study confirm that the Douyin platform significantly influences individual factors, including attitudes, preferences, and self-perceptions, particularly through algorithmic content delivery, influencer marketing, and emotionally engaging media. These effects are especially pronounced among younger users and females, highlighting the platform's strong resonance with specific demographic groups. The study contributes to a growing understanding of how social media platforms act as powerful agents in shaping individual behaviour and identity. However, several areas require further exploration. Future research should investigate the point at which digital natives begin to resist traditional behavioural norms and how they adapt to social expectations embedded in algorithmic recommendation systems. Delving into the psychological and cultural foundations of content rejection could offer a more nuanced understanding of digital identity formation and the evolution of social practices online. Lastly, emotional persuasion in digital environments deserves focused inquiry. Emotional elements such as humour, urgency, and nostalgia have proven more effective than rational arguments in influencing behaviour. Understanding how these emotional cues can be responsibly leveraged will be valuable not only for marketers, but also for educators, policy makers, and mental health professionals aiming to enhance digital communication strategies. Together, these research directions point toward the need for interdisciplinary models that better explain behavioural shifts in the age of algorithm-driven media and evolving digital identities.

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